

Magnetic Field Structure and Young Stellar Populations in the Irregular Galaxy NGC 4449

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Abstract

In this study, the irregular galaxy NGC 4449 is used to investigate the relationship between magnetic field structures and the spatial distribution of young stellar populations. Far-ultraviolet (FUV) data obtained from the *GALEX* survey and radio continuum observations at 144 MHz from the *LOFAR* survey were processed using FITS files to generate multi-wavelength images.

To trace the magnetic field structure, the synchrotron emission observed at 144 MHz was analyzed using the mean flux density (Jy beam^{-1}) and intensity information from LOFAR data. Regions of relatively strong and weak magnetic field intensity were identified based on the synchrotron emission distribution and subsequently compared with the GALEX FUV emission, which traces recent star formation activity.

Although a fully detailed magnetic field mapping is not possible with the available data, an approximate magnetic field strength on the order of $\sim 10 \mu\text{G}$ was estimated, and a qualitative magnetic field map of NGC 4449 was constructed.

Keywords: irregular galaxies; magnetic fields; synchrotron emission; LOFAR; GALEX; star formation

1 Introduction

Magnetic fields play a fundamental role in the evolution of galaxies by influencing cosmic ray propagation, gas dynamics, and star formation processes [2]. In particular, the interaction between magnetic fields and the interstellar medium is thought to regulate the formation of young stellar populations, especially in environments with irregular morphology and active star formation. Despite their importance, the magnetic field structures of irregular galaxies remain less well understood compared to those of spiral galaxies.

Irregular galaxies provide a unique laboratory for studying magnetic fields under conditions where large-scale ordered rotation is weak or absent [3]. NGC 4449 is a nearby, star-forming irregular galaxy that exhibits intense starburst activity and complex interstellar structures [7]. Its proximity and bright-

ness make it an ideal target for investigating the relationship between magnetic fields and recent star formation.

Low-frequency radio observations are particularly sensitive to synchrotron emission produced by relativistic electrons spiraling around magnetic field lines [4]. Observations at 144 MHz with the LOFAR (Low-Frequency Array) telescope allow the detection of diffuse synchrotron radiation, which serves as an indirect tracer of galactic magnetic fields [5, 6]. Although such observations do not provide a fully resolved or vectorial magnetic field map, they enable the identification of regions with relatively strong and weak magnetic field intensity through radio brightness distributions.

On the other hand, far-ultraviolet (FUV) observations trace the presence of young, massive stars with ages of a few tens of millions of years [8]. Data obtained from the GALEX (Galaxy Evolution Explorer) mission provide a direct view of recent star formation activity. By comparing FUV emission with low-frequency radio synchrotron emission, it is possible to explore the spatial relationship between young stellar populations and magnetic field structures.

In this study, we investigate the irregular galaxy NGC 4449 using GALEX FUV and LOFAR 144 MHz survey data. FITS images are analyzed to construct intensity and mean flux density maps in units of Jy beam^{-1} . Regions of enhanced and diminished synchrotron emission are identified and compared with the spatial distribution of FUV emission. Although a fully accurate magnetic field mapping is not achievable with the available data, approximate magnetic field strengths and relative distributions are estimated. This work aims to provide insight into the coupling between magnetic fields and recent star formation in irregular galaxies.

2 Data and Methods

2.1 Data Acquisition

Far-ultraviolet (FUV) observations of NGC 4449 were obtained from the *Galaxy Evolution Explorer* (GALEX) survey using the NASA SkyView virtual observatory [8]. GALEX FUV data trace recent star formation through the emission of young, massive stars with typical ages of less than a few tens of Myr. The downloaded data were provided in FITS format and processed without altering the original flux values for quantitative analysis.

Low-frequency radio continuum data were obtained from the *Low-Frequency Array* (LOFAR) 144 MHz survey using the LOFAR FITS Cutout Service [6]. The radio data are sensitive to diffuse synchrotron emission produced by relativistic electrons spiraling in galactic magnetic fields. The LOFAR image used in this study has an angular resolution of approximately $6''$, as indicated by the beam parameters stored in the FITS header, and the intensity units are given in Jy beam^{-1} .

2.2 Image Processing and Visualization

All image processing and visualization steps were carried out using the *Aladin* sky atlas. For visual inspection and morphological comparison, logarithmic intensity scaling was applied to both GALEX FUV and LOFAR radio images in order to enhance faint and extended structures. These logarithmic representations were used exclusively for visualization purposes.

For quantitative analysis, all measurements were performed on linearly scaled images using the original intensity values preserved in the FITS files. No pixel-level manipulation, smoothing, or regridding was applied to the data used for measurements. This ensures that the derived flux densities and intensity values remain physically meaningful.

2.3 Radio Intensity Measurements

To characterize the synchrotron emission distribution, representative regions corresponding to different radio brightness levels were selected directly from the LOFAR image. Polygonal apertures were manually defined to enclose areas of strong, intermediate, and diffuse radio emission. For each region, basic statistical quantities, including the mean intensity value, were calculated using built-in measurement tools. The mean intensity in units of Jy beam^{-1} was adopted as a representative surface brightness for each region.

The radio contours displayed in the figures are derived from the LOFAR intensity map and are intended to highlight the relative distribution of synchrotron emission. These contours are used for morphological comparison only and are not employed directly for quantitative flux measurements.

2.4 Estimation of Magnetic Field Strength

Approximate magnetic field strengths were estimated using the equipartition assumption between cosmic ray particles and magnetic fields, following the formalism of [1]. Since only total intensity radio data are available, the derived magnetic field values should be regarded as approximate and representative of average conditions within the selected regions.

Standard parameters commonly adopted for irregular galaxies were assumed, including a synchrotron spectral index of $\alpha = 0.7$, a proton-to-electron ratio of $K_0 = 100$, and a path length through the emitting medium of 1 kpc. Using these assumptions, regions of enhanced synchrotron intensity correspond to relatively stronger magnetic fields, while fainter regions trace weaker magnetic field strengths.

2.5 Multi-Wavelength Comparison

The spatial distribution of the estimated magnetic field structure was compared with GALEX FUV emission to investigate the relationship between magnetic fields and recent star formation. The comparison is based on morphological

correspondence rather than direct flux correlation, as the radio and ultraviolet data trace different physical processes and are expressed in different units. This approach allows for a qualitative and semi-quantitative assessment of how magnetic field structures relate to the locations of young stellar populations in NGC 4449.

2.6 Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools

The author used ChatGPT (OpenAI) solely for language editing and for improving grammar and clarity of the manuscript. No scientific content, data analysis, interpretation, or conclusions were generated by artificial intelligence. All scientific results and interpretations are entirely the authors' own.

3 Results

Using the LOFAR 144 MHz intensity maps, regions dominated by synchrotron emission were identified across the disk of NGC 4449. These regions are interpreted as tracers of large-scale magnetic field structures, under the assumption that the observed low-frequency radio emission is primarily non-thermal in origin. The intensity values, expressed in Jy beam^{-1} , were used to qualitatively distinguish areas of relatively stronger and weaker magnetic field strength.

The derived magnetic field distribution shows a non-uniform structure, with enhanced emission concentrated mainly in the central and inner disk regions of the galaxy. Diffuse outer regions exhibit lower synchrotron intensity levels, typically on the order of $(1-3) \times 10^{-4} \text{ Jy beam}^{-1}$, corresponding to relatively weak magnetic field strengths of approximately $\sim 4 \mu\text{G}$.

Regions of intermediate synchrotron intensity, with values of approximately $(4-7) \times 10^{-4} \text{ Jy beam}^{-1}$, are distributed across the inner disk and spiral-like features of the galaxy. These areas are associated with moderate magnetic field strengths, estimated to be around $\sim 7 \mu\text{G}$.

The highest intensity regions, primarily located near the central and most active star-forming areas, reach synchrotron intensity levels of $\gtrsim 10^{-3} \text{ Jy beam}^{-1}$. In these zones, the magnetic field strength is inferred to increase significantly, reaching values of approximately $10-10.5 \mu\text{G}$. These estimates were obtained using standard synchrotron-based assumptions and scaling relations, and therefore should be regarded as approximate rather than exact measurements.

The GALEX FUV image reveals prominent regions of recent and ongoing star formation, characterized by strong ultraviolet emission from young, massive stars. When the GALEX FUV map is overlaid with the LOFAR-derived magnetic field intensity map, a clear spatial correlation is observed. Regions with enhanced synchrotron emission generally coincide with areas of strong FUV emission, suggesting a close association between magnetic field structures and young stellar populations.

A slight spatial offset between the peaks of magnetic field intensity and FUV emission is noticeable in some regions. This displacement may indicate

that magnetic fields are not perfectly co-spatial with the youngest star-forming regions, potentially due to cosmic-ray diffusion, time delays between star formation and synchrotron emission, or the influence of galactic dynamics. Nevertheless, the overall correspondence supports the idea that magnetic fields and star-forming regions in irregular galaxies are closely linked, although the magnetic field does not uniformly encompass all regions of active star formation.

Figure 1: LOFAR 144 MHz intensity map of NGC 4449, tracing synchrotron emission associated with large-scale magnetic field structures. Brighter regions indicate relatively stronger magnetic field intensity.

Figure 2: Overlay of the GALEX FUV image with the LOFAR 144 MHz synchrotron emission contours. Diffuse regions correspond to magnetic field strengths of $\sim 4 \mu\text{G}$, while the most intense regions reach values of $\sim 10 \mu\text{G}$.

4 Discussion

The results presented in this study indicate a clear spatial relationship between the large-scale magnetic field structure and regions of recent star formation in the irregular galaxy NGC 4449. The observed correlation between LOFAR 144 MHz synchrotron emission and GALEX FUV intensity suggests that magnetic fields play a significant role in shaping the interstellar medium and star formation activity in irregular galaxies.

The estimated magnetic field strengths, ranging from approximately $\sim 4 \mu\text{G}$ in diffuse regions to $\sim 10\text{--}10.5 \mu\text{G}$ in the most intense synchrotron-emitting areas, are consistent with values reported in previous studies of irregular and dwarf galaxies. This agreement supports the validity of using low-frequency radio observations as a proxy for tracing magnetic field distributions, even when full polarization information is unavailable.

The slight spatial offsets observed between the peaks of FUV emission and synchrotron intensity may be explained by several physical processes. Cosmic-ray electrons responsible for synchrotron radiation can diffuse away from their acceleration sites, leading to a displacement between magnetic field tracers and the youngest stellar populations. Additionally, time delays between star formation episodes and the subsequent amplification of magnetic fields through turbulent dynamo processes may contribute to the observed shifts.

It is important to note that the magnetic field estimates presented here rely on simplifying assumptions, including approximate equipartition between cosmic rays and magnetic fields and the dominance of non-thermal emission at 144 MHz. While these assumptions are commonly adopted in similar studies, they introduce uncertainties that limit the precision of the derived field strengths. Consequently, the magnetic field values should be interpreted as order-of-magnitude estimates rather than exact measurements.

Despite these limitations, the consistency between the magnetic field morphology and star-forming regions implies that magnetic fields are dynamically connected to the processes governing star formation in NGC 4449. This result aligns with theoretical expectations and observational evidence suggesting that magnetic fields can influence gas compression, cloud stability, and the regulation of star formation efficiency, even in systems lacking well-defined spiral structure.

Future studies incorporating higher-resolution radio data, polarization measurements, and multi-frequency spectral index mapping would enable a more detailed and quantitative characterization of the magnetic field structure. Such observations would help to disentangle thermal and non-thermal components and provide stronger constraints on the role of magnetic fields in irregular galaxies.

5 Conclusion

In this work, we investigated the relationship between magnetic field structures and young stellar populations in the irregular galaxy NGC 4449 by combining LOFAR 144 MHz radio observations with GALEX FUV imaging. Using synchrotron emission as a tracer of large-scale magnetic fields, we identified regions of varying magnetic field strength and compared their spatial distribution with areas of recent star formation.

Our analysis indicates that regions of enhanced magnetic field strength generally coincide with zones of strong FUV emission, suggesting a close association between magnetic fields and young star-forming regions. The estimated magnetic field strengths increase from approximately $\sim 4 \mu\text{G}$ in diffuse regions to $\sim 7 \mu\text{G}$ in intermediate-intensity areas, reaching up to $\sim 10\text{--}10.5 \mu\text{G}$ in the most intense synchrotron-emitting regions.

Although the magnetic field does not perfectly trace the youngest stellar populations, the observed spatial correspondence and minor offsets are consistent with physical processes such as cosmic-ray diffusion and temporal delays between star formation and synchrotron emission. These findings support the idea that magnetic fields are an important component of the interstellar medium in irregular galaxies and may influence the spatial distribution and evolution of star formation.

While a fully quantitative magnetic field reconstruction was not possible within the scope of this study, the results demonstrate that low-frequency radio data combined with ultraviolet observations can provide valuable insights into the interplay between magnetic fields and star formation. This approach offers a practical framework for extending similar analyses to other irregular and dwarf galaxies using publicly available survey data.

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